

Factors Influencing Success in Business

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Abstract

Many Business people would argue that there is not one concrete recipe for success. But many successful businesses have in certain common characteristics that have contributed to the rise of business success. Operating a successful business is not just about working hard, but rather about working smart. Smart work means that improving planning, Management and targeting along with many other things. This paper explains several key factors that influence the success of the business. These factors help to assist management in measuring whether they are on track toward reaching profit and market share goals.

Introduction

When an entrepreneur opens a business, a great deal of work goes into making the business a success. An experienced business professional tells that success in business is planned and does not happen by accident. Approximately 99% of new start-ups fail in the first ten years and the primary reason for this high rate of failure is that most entrepreneurs start a business unprepared and with the wrong mindset. Business success depends on entrepreneurs, his skills and resources and ability to bring customers to the table. Entrepreneurs are the ultimate critical success for any business. Now the dream of becoming successful in running a business captures the imagination of aspiring businessmen. This is a where a vision of thrilled customers, balanced profits and industry respect comes in – and it is possible to fulfill each by understanding the factors that make a business successful. The success factor for any organization are directly related to what an organization is, and how it operates in the world. To survive as a human, we need food, water, the right temperature range and protection from danger. What an organization needs to survive.

Essentially five things are needed by an organization wanting to succeed:

- People- those who make up the organization.
- Purpose- a reason for organizing and working together
- Purpose- activities which the people undertake to fulfill their purpose

- Physical resources- a place to work, the right equipment, money to pay the bills and the people who work there
- Customers-People outside the organization who is willing to pay money in return for the products and services the organization provides; for government organizations taxpayers are the customers; many nonprofits depend on contributions from donors who believe in the value of what the organization is doing.

Several factors contribute to the success of a business and understanding what they are and how they work together can help the business succeed.

“The 5 Key Success Factors – A Powerful System For Total Business Success”

Managing and Developing People

People today want some direction and structure, but they also want freedom and encouragement to develop their skills and knowledge. Effectively managing people requires balancing constraining forces (Providing direction, Structure, Organization, Some rules) with liberating forces. Each person has a different set of needs for structure vs. freedom, order vs. opportunity, logic vs. personal values, factual information vs. meaning and connections, and so on. Effective managers do not manage all people the same, except for the same basic rules. They manage each person according to what he or she needs, what motivates them to do their best. This can be complicated but is essential for success.

Strategic Focus

Leaders have to focus the organization’s resources on the greatest opportunities, which shift with each new day. Doors open and doors close. Major customers or income sources can change or even go out of business at any time. So it’s necessary for leaders to keep focused on the desired results such as increased sales and profits, or more satisfied customers, while constantly steering the organization across the stormy waters of the marketplace.

Operations, or What People Do all Day

Effective Operations ensure that customers get exactly what they want at the right time and the right quality. Thus the effective operations management focus on what is called cycle time (producing a product or service from start to finish), cost control, and quality control. Communication is the true lifeblood of a successful organization- a high flow of information, so everyone and everything is connected.

Physical Resources

One of the biggest expenses is providing adequate facilities and equipment for people to work in and with. Experienced managers learn that cash flow is king. Failing to manage cash flow is the No.1 reason for business failure. Too many business owners leave the money up to someone else and can easily get blind-sided when suddenly the money isn’t there to keep the doors open. The economy is always cyclical. So buy nice facilities when times are good, paying for them can be difficult or impossible in a downturn.

Customer Relations

Customers are where the money comes from; this is the most important success factor. The purpose of a business is to get and keep customers. Getting customers involves marketing- indeed this success factor includes all kinds of marketing and sales. Effective sales and marketing begin with asking existing and potential customers what they need, what problem they want solved or deficiency filled.

Here are the additional success factors that are key to a start up with a services offering

The Right Mindset

“A successful business is created before there is a business.” –Rich Dad.

The mindset is the foundation of every successful business and the reason is perception determines the way in the success of the business. Mindset determines the business mission, its vision, business culture and work ethics.

Most people start a business because they believe building a business is the fastest way to Make money and get rich. Some start a business because they want to be their boss and do things their way; while others start a business just to pay themselves a decent check monthly. While making money from your business is not a bad idea, the primary aim of business success is to provide value and take care of the customers.

Building a successful business is not an overnight hit. It is a product of continuous effort in the right in the direction. Secondly, running a business is never a smooth ride. It involves adequately for the challenges. Lack of preparedness on the part of the entrepreneur has caused the collapse of many businesses.

The Right Business Idea

The next factor that makes a business successful is a great business idea. Because a great idea translates into a great product. The most important success factor is that the idea must ultimately have demand. It must either solve a problem or satisfy a need; this, in turn, will create a market.

Capital

Capital is crucial to the success and survival of all types of business. But the critical point is that capital is not the most important factor for building a successful business. The reason businesses with excess liquidity. So it's not all about having the money, it's all about knowing how to use the money and having the right people to execute the plans.

A Great Team

Assembling a business team that provides strategic direction and execution of plans. Every member of the team must be competent, tested and proven in their various fields. To obtain the best result, it is advisable to split the team into two (Internal and external team). Internal team should comprise of individuals that see to the smooth daily operations of business. They include your accountant, operations manager, product development team, etc. External team, on the other hand, may not exist within the business, yet they provide strategic professional services and advice need to grow the business. Those should havean your external team include an advisor, mentor, consultants, attorney or lawyer, banker, tax strategist, etc.

The Right Timing

Nothing kills a business faster than irrational decision making, taking miscalculated risks or making ill-timed business moves. To reach the pinnacle of success in business, Entrepreneur must have a strategic plan and a team to execute such a plan. The entrepreneur must execute such a plan at the right time. Thus, Entrepreneur must know when to wait, when to act and when to act fast.

Network

Most entrepreneurs know the power of inner networks. It helps to strengthen the relationship with peers, mentors and other key players from the business to the entrepreneur. Inner networks provide direction, support, and a growing number of people to help.

Adaptability

Successful stems from its ability to adapt to changes. The world of business is filled with startling events and surprises. In other words, it is never static and it is unpredictable. Adaptability allows the Entrepreneur to respond to circumstances and stay competitive. It keeps business in a liquid state, thereby making business adapt to any situation whatsoever.

Integrity

Important criteria for building a successful business is integrity. Being honest and open business helps the company grow and develop entrepreneurial individuality. The entrepreneur was honest with his employees, customers, suppliers, associate, investors, etc. One thing about integrity is that it will take please, never doubt it.

Competence

Without competence, all other factors are null and void. Even with all the capital, ideas and customers in the world, if the entrepreneurs are not competent enough to handle them, will lose them in due time. Competence is a combination of knowledge about the business through the understanding of the industry and experience built over the years.

Customer Loyalty

Business cannot serve customers; then it is dead on arrival. But serving customers is not enough to ensure business survival and eventual success. To succeed, Entrepreneur needs to raise an army of loyal customers and to achieve such; he needs to make them a specific promise and deliver on such promise.

Conclusion

Starting a business is complex, time-consuming and life-altering. There are many more things that go into running it. The entrepreneur is responsible for business's finances, protecting business and personal assets, paying taxes, keeping records, managing employees and total business success.

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